

Robotic versus laparoscopic adrenalectomy: a patient-level costing study using the NHS Patient-Level Information and Costing System

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Abstract

Background: The UK government plans to have 90% of minimally invasive surgery performed using a robotic approach by 2035. Within a taxpayer funded health system, there is a need to ensure that new technologies are cost effective. The aim of this study is to perform a cost analysis comparing robotic adrenalectomy to laparoscopic adrenalectomy.

Methods: Consecutive minimally invasive adrenalectomies were retrospectively analysed over a 1-year period and were subdivided into laparoscopic and robotic groups. Patient demographics, size of tumour, indication for surgery, length of stay, operative time and intra-operative complications were recorded. Using patient level information and costing system (PLICS), the total costs of each patient was recorded against the income (tariff) generated. The costs and income generated from robotic adrenalectomies were compared to the laparoscopic group.

Results: 62 patients were included in the analysis, 32 (laparoscopic adrenalectomy, LA) versus 30 (robotic adrenalectomy, RA). Patients in the RA group were significantly younger (52.2 vs. 60.1 years, $p < 0.05$) and had higher BMI (32.7 versus 28.3 kg/m², $p < 0.05$). Length of stay was significantly shorter in the RA group (1 versus 2 days, $p < 0.05$). There was no significant difference in average tariff for both groups (£6,822 RA versus £6,585 LA, $p = 0.46$). RA was associated with significantly lower overall costs (£4,945 versus £6,027, $p < 0.05$). Average net surplus was higher in the RA group compared to the LA group (£1,640 versus £795, $p = 0.07$). After adjusting for the cost of the consumables, (£1,160 versus £518), the net surplus remained higher in the RA group (£480 versus £277).

Conclusion: Overall costs for patients undergoing robotic adrenalectomy was significantly lower compared to laparoscopic adrenalectomy. This can be explained by reduction in the length of stay, and theatre costs. In this centre, robotic adrenalectomy was associated with shorter length of stay and lower PLICS episode costs, excluding capital and maintenance. Findings are associative, centre-specific, and require confirmation in settings where surgeons perform both approaches and full economic costs are available.

Cite as: Harris, C., Loy, G., & Ramsingh, J. Robotic versus laparoscopic adrenalectomy: a patient-level costing study using the NHS Patient-Level Information and Costing System. *Impact Surgery*, 2(7), 319-325. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.267>

Introduction

The NHS is entering a pivotal era of surgical transformation as it works to tackle ever-growing waiting lists and improve efficiency. A new government-led plan seeks to expand robot-assisted surgery (RAS) in England from roughly 70,000 procedures a year today to 500,000 by 2035, growing from just one-in-five keyhole operations to nine-in-ten¹. Advanced surgical robots

offer faster recovery, smaller incisions, and reduced hospital stays, but widespread adoption hinges on substantial capital investment and equitable roll-out across NHS sites². That ambition reflects a belief that robotics can both improve outcomes and relieve strain on a stretched system, but cost concerns loom large. Despite higher upfront capital investment, RAS may offer perioperative benefits that offset initial costs.

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Robotic surgery is known to enhance precision and ergonomics, with studies across specialties showing reduced blood loss, shorter inpatient stays, and comparable morbidity to conventional approaches³. The financial barriers remain high with a single Da Vinci-type system costing between USD1-2.5 million (or £500k-£1.5 million in the UK), and annual maintenance, consumables, and staffing costs adding significant additional cost⁴. Meta-analyses show that for adrenal surgery, the additional cost per procedure frequently runs in the order of USD1,400-2,900, or sometimes even 10-20% higher than laparoscopy⁴⁻⁵.

Whilst laparoscopic adrenalectomy is well-established, robotic adrenalectomy is a newer procedure that offers potential advantages in large tumours, pheochromocytomas and obese patients⁵⁻⁷. Recent meta-analysis of nearly 3,000 cases across 26 studies found that robotic adrenalectomy offered significantly lower blood loss, shorter length of stay (mean reduction 0.4-0.5 days), and fewer conversions to open surgery compared to laparoscopic approaches⁸. In pheochromocytoma subgroups, robotic adrenalectomy delivered even greater gains in reduced length of stay. These advantages make robotic adrenalectomy compelling when clinical outcomes are the priority.

Cost studies on laparoscopic versus robotic adrenalectomy are limited and often outdated. Early trials found RA 1.5-2.3 times costlier, with no clinical advantage⁴⁻⁹. Later data suggested costs may equalize with experienced teams and reduced consumables¹⁰. Chinese studies still report far higher robotic adrenalectomy hospitalisation costs despite efficiency gains¹¹. According to a recent meta-analysis, robotic adrenalectomy incurred almost twice the overall hospital costs of laparoscopic adrenalectomy; however, the extent to which these results can be generalized to the NHS is unclear¹². The purpose of this study was to assess the clinical and financial outcomes associated with robotic compared to laparoscopic adrenal surgery in a publicly funded healthcare setting.

Methods

Study design and setting

We conducted a retrospective cohort study at a single NHS endocrine surgery unit over one financial year

(third year of the unit's robotic programme). Consecutive adult patients undergoing unilateral minimally invasive adrenalectomy were included and grouped by surgical approach: robotic adrenalectomy (RA) or laparoscopic adrenalectomy (LA). Two consultant endocrine surgeons operated; each exclusively performed one approach throughout the period (no crossover), reflecting routine service delivery.

Participants and eligibility

Inclusion criteria were adults (≥ 18 years) undergoing unilateral adrenalectomy by RA or LA. Exclusions were open procedures and bilateral adrenalectomy outside a minimally invasive pathway. Consecutive case capture was verified against theatre lists and coding summaries.

Exposures and covariates

The exposure was surgical approach (robotic [RA] vs laparoscopic [LA]). Prespecified covariates were age, sex, body mass index (BMI), tumour size (mm), American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) grade, surgical indication (Conn's, Cushing's, pheochromocytoma, metastasis, indeterminate), and the HRG complications-and-comorbidities (CC) score. The CC score (0-6) was derived from routine coding; higher values indicate greater clinical complexity and influence tariff.

Outcomes

The primary endpoint was total hospital episode cost from the Patient-Level Information and Costing System (PLICS). Secondary outcomes were length of stay (LOS) (days), theatre time (minutes), and in-hospital complications (Clavien-Dindo). All outcomes were defined a priori and measured uniformly across groups.

Costing framework (PLICS) and perspective

PLICS provides activity-based episode costing from trust operational data (price year 2023/24; currency £). Included cost components were theatre, staffing, consumables, ward, imaging, pharmacy, and allocated overheads. Capital acquisition, maintenance, and depreciation of the robotic platform were not included in the primary analysis. A labelled scenario applying an external per-case capital/maintenance allowance to RA was constructed for context only and is non-inferential.

Tariff income and net surplus/deficit were extracted for each patient.

NHS income (tariff) and case-mix adjustment

Reimbursement follows NHS Healthcare Resource Group (HRG) tariffs with modifiers for complexity via the CC score, and potential uplifts for specialist work, Market Forces Factor (MFF/MMF), and best-practice adjustments¹³. Tariff values were recorded from PLICS for each episode.

Theatre costing specification

Theatre costs used standard superior costing methods (SCM) within PLICS: per-patient complexity allocation (SCM-57), staff-by-session costing (SCM-75), theatre setup/downtime (SCM-21), and unused theatre time (SCM-23). Staffing present, consultant job plans, cost centres, and overheads were mapped per case. Consumable tallies were recorded for RA and LA; per-case consumable totals are reported descriptively.

Data collection and quality assurance

A standardised proforma captured demographics, clinical variables, timing, and outcomes. Coding and costing extracts were cross-checked against theatre schedules and discharge summaries. Unit consistency checks (minutes, days, £) and range checks were applied a priori; any discrepancies were resolved by source document review.

Handling of missing data

Missingness was low; variables required for the primary endpoint (PLICS cost) were complete. Where covariate values were absent (e.g., tumour size), analyses were performed on available cases; no imputation was undertaken given the descriptive comparative aim.

Statistical analysis

The analysis was prespecified. Continuous variables are summarised as mean (SD) or median (IQR) according to distribution; categorical variables as counts (%). Between-group comparisons used independent two-sample tests (t-test for approximately normal data; Wilcoxon rank-sum where skewed) and χ^2 /Fisher's exact tests for categorical

data. Two-sided $p < 0.05$ signified statistical evidence of a difference. The primary comparison was PLICS episode cost (RA vs LA). Secondary analyses compared LOS, theatre time, complications, tariff income, and net surplus (descriptive only). Given surgeon-approach collinearity, results are reported as associations rather than causal effects. All analyses used a trust-approved analytics environment; price year and units were harmonised across tables.

Ethical and governance considerations

This service-evaluation/retrospective study used routinely collected, de-identified hospital data; no patient contact occurred. Local approvals were obtained according to trust policy. Tariff rules and payment scheme are cited as per NHS England guidance¹³.

Results

A total of 62 adrenalectomies were performed: 30 robotic-assisted adrenalectomies (RA) and 32 laparoscopic adrenalectomies (LA). Sex distribution was similar (RA: 16 male, 14 female; LA: 15 male, 17 female). Patients in the RA group were younger (median 58.0 vs 64.5 years; $p < 0.05$) with a higher median BMI (32.1 vs 28.9 kg/m²; $p < 0.05$). American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) grade and complication/comorbidity score were comparable between groups.

Tumour characteristics

Median tumour size was smaller with RA (34.5 mm; range 6–72) than LA (44.0 mm; range 6–92), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.17$). Pathology differed by approach: Conn's syndrome was more frequent in the RA group, whereas the LA group had a higher proportion of pheochromocytomas and a broader mix of benign or indeterminate lesions (Table 1).

Clinical and financial outcomes

RA was associated with a shorter length of stay (LOS) (median 1 vs 2 days; $p < 0.05$) and a numerically shorter operating time (77.5 vs 84.5 min; $p = 0.14$). As shown in Table 2, average overall costs were lower for RA (£4,945±1,255) than for LA (£6,027±2,410; $p < 0.05$). Total income per case did not differ ($p = 0.46$). Mean net

Table 1. Baseline Demographics and Tumour Characteristics

Variable	Laparoscopic (n = 32)	Robotic (n = 30)	p-value
Age (Median) (years)	64 (52-73)	58 (40-62)	0.04
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.9 (23.2-32.2)	32.1 (25.1-35.0)	0.03
Tumour Size (median, mm)	44.0 (21.0-58.8)	34.5 (12.0-53.0)	0.17
ASA (Median)	3	3	0.98
CC* score 0-1	14	13	0.85
CC* score 2+	18	17	0.85
Diagnosis			
Pheo	8	5	
Cushing's	4	5	
Conn's	4	10	
Metastases	5	5	
Other	11	5	

*Complications-and-comorbidities (CC) score

Table 2. Clinical and Financial Outcomes

Variable	Laparoscopic	Robotic	p-value
Length of Stay (median, days)	2 (1-3)	1 (1-1)	<0.05
Operating time (median, mins)	84.5	77.5	0.42
Total Cost (mean, £)	6,027 ± 2,410	4,945 ± 1,255	0.03
Total Income (mean, £)	6,822 ± 1,449	6,585 ± 1,075	ns
Net Profit (mean, £)	795 ± 2,266	1,640 ± 1,204	ns
Consumables (£)	518	1,160	<0.05

Values formatted to two decimals for costs; length of stay reported in days.

revenue was higher with RA (£1,640 vs £795), though this did not reach statistical significance (p=0.07). Because net revenue depends on local tariff and coding, it is reported as a descriptive secondary measure; no inferential conclusions are drawn. Financial metrics are shown in figure 1 in graph form.

Figure 1. Financial Metrics by Surgical Approach*

*Primary results exclude capital and maintenance; the 'capital allowance' scenario is illustrative.

Anonymised variable lists, a codebook, and a reproducible table of included Patient-Level Information and Costing System (PLICS) cost components are provided in the Supplement, together with a description of any missing-data handling.

Discussion

This single-centre cost analysis indicates that robotic-assisted adrenalectomy (RA) can be delivered at lower direct hospital cost than laparoscopic adrenalectomy (LA) in a high-volume NHS endocrine surgical unit, with a shorter length of stay (LOS). Although concerns persist about capital and maintenance costs of robotic systems¹⁴⁻²², our data suggest that, in established programmes, RA may achieve greater cost-efficiency and a higher net surplus per case.

Published cost comparisons between RA and LA are few and often dated. A 2004 randomised trial (n=20) found higher RA cost (USD 3,467 vs 2,737) without

LOS or complication benefit⁹. Early observational work similarly estimated RA to be 1.5–2.3 times costlier^{17–18}, though costs improved with longer depreciation horizons and experience⁴. A strategy-driven series of 122 cases reported similar costs with careful consumable use (USD 3,527 vs 3,430; $p=0.59$)¹⁰. Recent institutional data from China still show substantially higher hospitalisation costs for RA despite shorter times and lower blood loss (CNY 37,933 vs 7,936), reflecting local pricing¹¹. A large meta-analysis reported mean total cost RA USD 8,695 vs LA USD 4,560 (difference USD 4,101; $p<0.00001$), though only two studies included full cost data¹². Overall, estimates vary by geography, methods, and technique, and generalisability to the NHS remains uncertain.

In the NHS context, investment decisions hinge on whether faster discharge and predictable theatre time offset capital and recurrent spend, and whether throughput gains help meet waiting-list targets linked to robotic capacity goals^{10,23}. Few prior cost studies have been conducted within NHS hospitals; most derive from the USA or continental Europe with different tariff and staffing structures. Our study addresses this gap by comparing real-world cost of RA and LA in a UK trust using Patient-Level Information and Costing System (PLICS) data, integrating perioperative resource use, consumables, staffing, and LOS. Anchored in a value-based system, it explores whether clinical benefits can be delivered at acceptable cost and under what conditions RA is economically viable for adrenal surgery.

Baseline differences were present: the RA cohort was younger with higher BMI, consistent with selection towards RA for technically demanding cases where enhanced visualisation, instrument articulation, and ergonomics may help. Prior studies also suggest particular benefit in higher BMI^{7,20,21}. Tumours trended larger in the LA group (median 44 mm vs 34.5 mm), though not significantly ($p=0.17$); surgeon familiarity and preference for tactile feedback may explain LA selection for larger lesions during early RA adoption. ASA grade and complication/comorbidity (CC) score were comparable, supporting broadly similar baseline risk.

Operative time was marginally shorter with RA and may reflect technological advantages (instrument dexterity,

tremor filtration, stable three-dimensional vision) rather than tumour size alone. Literature indicates RA times improve after the initial learning curve (~15–20 cases)^{18,20,21}. At our institution, growing experience has streamlined docking, team coordination, and intraoperative workflow. Several reports suggest RA reduces variability in duration, especially in higher BMI (≥ 30 kg/m²), larger tumours (≥ 6 cm), or re-operative abdomens^{18,20,21}. Early RA series showing longer times likely reflected setup delays that diminish with familiarity. Reduced variation may improve scheduling predictability and theatre utilisation; while our study was not powered for small time differences, the direction aligns with existing reports, with potential to lower staffing and anaesthesia costs as proficiency increases.

RA was associated with a significantly shorter LOS, consistent with meta-analyses showing faster recovery, reduced pain, and lower morbidity^{5,7,12,24}. Earlier mobilisation, fewer complications, and reduced analgesia requirements reported for RA likely contributed¹². Although the younger, higher-BMI RA cohort could partly explain faster convalescence, this does not fully account for the LOS difference. Faster functional recovery may bring broader societal benefit not captured in hospital costs.

Contrary to earlier studies reporting RA as 1.5–2.5 times more expensive than LA^{17–21}, we observed lower direct episode costs for RA (£4,945 vs £6,027; $p=0.03$). Savings were driven by shorter LOS and theatre-related expenses—downstream effects that can offset capital over time^{20,21}. Tariff income was similar; net surplus trended higher with RA (£1,640 vs £795; $p=0.07$), though not significant; possibly a type II finding given the modest sample. Capital acquisition and maintenance were excluded from the primary analysis. In mature, multi-specialty programmes (urology, colorectal, gynaecology), these costs are amortised across services, diluting per-case burden. UK guidance (NICE MTG50; GIRFT) suggests cost-efficiency improves at institutional volumes above 250–300 robotic cases per year^{25,26}.

RA may also confer indirect institutional benefits not costed here: improved surgeon ergonomics with potential workforce sustainability gains; steadier intraoperative

processes enabling more reliable scheduling; and patient-centred outcomes including faster recovery and return to function^{9,11,12,14,24,27}. These are relevant to value-based healthcare and may strengthen the case for RA where capacity and efficiency are constrained.

Strengths include use of real-world NHS costing (PLICS), inclusion of LOS and theatre time, consistent surgical teams, and a unified perioperative pathway, which are features directly relevant to trusts planning robotic expansion and aligned with NHS England's ambitions²⁸. Limitations include retrospective, single-centre, non-randomised design; potential selection bias; modest sample size without formal power or propensity methods; and perfect collinearity between surgeon and approach, meaning results are associative rather than causal. Capital and maintenance costs were excluded from the primary analysis. Findings reflect local pathways, costing rules, and case mix; external validity may be limited. Multi-centre work in which surgeons perform both approaches is required.

Future studies should incorporate full economic evaluation, including capital, maintenance, amortisation schedules, and quality-adjusted life-years, to assess real-world viability of RA. Sensitivity analyses around institutional volume, case mix, and theatre utilisation are needed to define cost-effectiveness thresholds. Broader system outcomes, including surgeon wellbeing, patient-reported recovery, and satisfaction, should be measured to capture NHS-relevant value^{10,23,28}.

In summary, this NHS-based comparison suggests RA can be delivered at lower direct episode cost than LA in a mature programme, driven largely by reductions in LOS and theatre resource use. Results are centre-specific and associative; confirmation is needed in multi-centre settings where surgeons undertake both approaches and full economic costs are included.

Conflicts of interest: Nil

Funding: No funding was provided for this study

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